

Studies on Electrostatic Effect and Tetrad Effect in some Mixed-ligand Lanthanide Complexes with Alizarine Red Sulphonate

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The influence of electrostatic effect accompanying the formation of mixed-ligand complexes of the type [MAL], where $M = \text{La}^{\text{III}}, \text{Ce}^{\text{III}}, \text{Pr}^{\text{III}}, \text{Nd}^{\text{III}}, \text{Sm}^{\text{III}}, \text{Eu}^{\text{III}}, \text{Gd}^{\text{III}}, \text{Tb}^{\text{III}}$ or Dy^{III} ; A = (primary ligand) CDTA or DTPA; L = (secondary ligand) alizarine red sulphonate (ARS), has been studied by comparing the formation constants of 1 : 1 binary ($\log K_{\text{ML}}^{\text{M}}$) and 1 : 1 : 1 ternary ($\log K_{\text{MAL}}^{\text{MA}}$) complexes. The formation constants have been determined at 25° in aqueous medium by using the Irving-Rossotti approach at an ionic strength, $I = 0.2$ (mol dm^{-3} , NaClO_4). The $\Delta \log K$ ($= \log K_{\text{MAL}}^{\text{MA}} - \log K_{\text{ML}}^{\text{M}}$) values have been found to be more negative with DTPA than with CDTA due to greater electrostatic repulsion with the former. The occurrence of tetrad effect has been discussed. The nature of M-L bond and some stability correlations have also been studied.

THE electrostatic effect may play a prominent role in affecting the solution stabilities of mixed-ligand complexes with charged (ionic) ligands¹. In view of their large ionic radii and high coordination numbers the trivalent lanthanide metal ions seem to be ideally suited for these investigations.

The present work reports the influence of electrostatic effect associated with the formation of some mixed-ligand lanthanide complexes of the type (MAL), where M = trivalent cation La, Ce, Pr, Nd, Sm, Eu, Gd, Tb or Dy; A = (primary ligand anion) CDTA or DTPA; L = (secondary ligand anion) alizarine red sulphonate (ARS). An attempt has been made to discuss the so-called tetrad-effect^{2,3} (initially called the gadolinium-break or the half-filled shell effect, and then the 'double-double effect' also) involved in the variation of stability of the lanthanide complexes with the number of their 4f-electrons.

Experimental

The nitrates (99.9% purity) of the trivalent lanthanides were obtained from Indian Rare Earths Ltd. All the solutions were prepared in double-distilled water. The metal content was estimated by complexometric titrations⁴. Other chemicals were also of standard purity, Sigma/Merck (G.R.)/ (AnalaR). A Elico LI-120 digital pH meter was used for pH measurements. Irving-Rossotti approach^{5,6} was used for determining the formation constants at 25° and an ionic strength, $I = 0.2$ (mol dm^{-3} , NaClO_4). The usual titration sets using 1×10^{-3} mol dm^{-3} solutions were prepared, equilibrated and titrated (to obtain reproducible pH data)

against a carbonate-free 0.2 mol dm^{-3} NaOH solution. A representative set of titration curves for the system (Ce.CDTA.ARS) is presented in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Representative pH-titration curves for the system (Ce.CDTA.ARS): (a) reference, (L) secondary ligand, (MA) primary complex, (ML) binary complex, and (MAL) ternary complex.

TABLE 1—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF BINARY AND TERNARY LANTHANIDE COMPLEXES
Temp. = 25° I = 0.2 mol dm⁻³ (NaClO₄)

Parameter	Tervalent lanthanide metal ion								
	La	Ce	Pr	Nd	Sm	Eu	Gd	Tb	Dy
log K _{M.ARS} ^M	9.85	10.06	10.07	10.20	10.24	10.32	10.18	10.34	10.37
log K _{M.CDTA.ARS} ^{M.CDTA}	5.20	5.32	5.36	5.42	5.94	6.08	6.03	6.74	6.80
-Δ log K	4.65	4.74	4.71	4.78	4.30	4.24	4.15	3.60	3.57
log K _{M.DTPA.ARS} ^{M.DTPA}	4.55	5.20	5.21	5.25	5.28	5.38	5.02	5.12	5.32
-Δ log K	5.30	4.86	4.86	4.95	4.96	4.94	5.16	5.22	5.05

Standard deviation = ±0.01 to ±0.03.

The use of dilute solutions minimised the possibility of formation of polymeric species; this was further ascertained by means of smooth plots (not shown) between $\bar{n}/(L)$ vs (L) , where \bar{n} = formation function and (L) = free-ligand concentration. Even otherwise, with polydentate ligands like CDTA (denticity six) and DTPA (denticity eight) the formation of species like MA₂ is improbable and hence the disproportionation of mixed complexes (2 MAL ⇌ MA₂ + ML₂) need not be considered. The presence of hydroxo species has been ignored in view of the nature of titration curves and relatively lower pH regions used for calculations.

Results and Discussion

The experimental values of the formation constants and Δ log K are presented in Table 1. The data were subjected to Q-test⁷ so as to reject any statistically suspect value. The formation of MAL complexes may be represented by equations (1) and (2),

where, M = trivalent lanthanide ion; A = CDTA⁴⁻, DTPA⁵⁻; L = ARS²⁻.

Formation of MA in the two cases involves a reaction between ions of opposite charge hence this step should be associated with a large entropy change which should be further increasingly favourable along the lanthanide series. In the second step, MAL is formed by a combination of two similarly charged species involving an electrostatic repulsion. This explains large negative values of Δ log K. The consequence of this repulsion accompanying the formation of MAL is further evident through larger (negative) values of Δ log K with DTPA than with CDTA as with the former there should be greater repulsion. The electrostatic effect leads to the stability sequence, DTPA < CDTA for the MAL complexes, whereas for the MA species the reverse order (DTPA > CDTA) is evident. The Δ log K may be looked upon in yet another way. Steric hindrance should increase

from ML (or MA) to MAL, and greater hindrance should exist with a larger DTPA anion. Statistical considerations further support the above conclusions.

Mathematical relationships between various formation constants have already been derived and tested for some ternary lanthanide complexes⁸. The present set of values leads to linear plots between log K_{MAL}^{MA} and log K_{ML}^M for the two primary ligands (curves not shown). The best straight line equations derived by using the method of least-squares are of the type,

$$\log K_{MAL}^{MA} = a \log K_{ML}^M - b \quad (3)$$

where, a and b are constants; for A = CDTA⁴⁻, a and b are 3.45 and 29.31, for A = DTPA⁵⁻, a and b are 1.19 and 7.00, respectively. The slope value is significantly smaller for DTPA as the octadentate DTPA anion leaves much less scope for sequential increase in log K_{MAL}^{MA} as against the hexadentate CDTA.

The tetrad effect: The observed stability sequence (Table 1) with respect to lanthanide cations is La < Ce < Pr < Nd < Sm < Eu > Gd < Tb < Dy for the binary as well as ternary complexes. Although a decrease in stability at Gd^{III} (4f⁷, i.e. half-filled shell) is seen clearly, but a better picture emerges on examining the plots (not shown) between the formation constants and the number of 4f-electrons. A prominent dip is seen at Gd^{III}, but in addition to this, particularly in the case of (M.CDTA.ARS), a weaker break is visible at Nd^{III} (4f⁸, i.e. approximately the quarter-filled shell). The non-availability of higher lanthanides has not permitted us to examine a possible break around Er^{III} (4f¹¹, i.e. approximately the three-quarter-filled shell). This tetrad-effect⁹ has been observed by some workers not only for the variation in solution stabilities of binary complexes^{2,9,10} but also for other thermodynamic properties¹¹⁻¹⁴. A satisfactory and convincing explanation of this phenomenon is, however, lacking in spite of several attempts^{2,9,9-14}.

An electrostatic model seems to hold good for the lanthanide complexes, the complexation interac-

tions being of the ion-dipole type. Born relation,

$$E = Z^2/2r.(1 - 1/D)$$

where, E = energy of reaction, Z = ionic charge, r = ionic radius of lanthanide ion, D = dielectric constant of the medium, has been found to hold good¹⁵ for their binary and ternary complexes also by showing that the plots of $\log K$ (or ΔG) vs Z^2/r are almost linear. Similar plots (not shown) in the present case contain a break at Gd^{III} besides some curvature, which is generally observed. It may also be noticed that the polarising power (Z/r^2) of the lanthanide (+3) ions increases by 30% on going from La to Dy, the ionic radius falls by 12.3% and hence a slight tendency of covalency, although the 4f-orbitals in the yttrium group are deeper. The complexes should be mainly entropy stabilised¹⁶. Here again the plots of $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ or $\log K_{ML}^M$ vs standard entropy (S_M°) of the lanthanide (+3) ions are roughly linear showing entropy stabilisation of the complexes, but the curves contain two segments with a break at Gd^{III} (Fig. 2). These plots resemble the S-shaped curves of enthalpy/entropy change (ΔH or ΔS) of complexation vs

Fig. 2. Variation in formation constant values with the standard entropies (S_M° cal K^{-1} mol $^{-1}$) of lanthanide elements: (A) $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ with CDTA, (B) $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ with DTPA, and (C) $\log K_{ML}^M$ with ARS.

number of 4f-electrons². The $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ values of the present series with CDTA as a representative case have been plotted against total orbital angular momentum values in Fig. 3. Only the first three segments are possible upto Dy^{III} , some curvature is also seen. It is obvious that larger the dip at Gd^{III} in the stability sequence greater will be the curvature in the second segment. Williams⁹ has recently pointed out that variation in ionic radii (lanthanide contraction) is basically a ligand field effect⁸. The angular terms of the ligand field are perhaps of smaller consequence than the radial

Fig. 3. Inclined-W type plots of $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ (with CDTA) vs total orbital angular momentum values (L_{LN}) of the lanthanides.

terms. If it is so, the electron-electron repulsions should cause an uneven decrease in the ionic radii of lanthanide (+3) ions and this may lead to the occurrence of tetrad effects, which correlates closely with the changes in magnetic quantum number although energetics of complexation are not related to magnetic energies.

In the present case, for example, from La^{III} to Dy^{III} there is an over all decrease in ionic radii by $\sim 12.3\%$, increase in ionic potential by $\sim 14.0\%$ and in the sum of the first three ionisation potentials by $\sim 11.6\%$. The electronegativity variations are small (positive as well as negative) and an over all increase of only $\sim 1.85\%$ occurs upto Dy^{III} . Whereas the $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ values for CDTA have been found to increase by $\sim 30\%$, those for DTPA register a much smaller increase of $\sim 17\%$ which may possibly be due to a larger size and denticity of DTPA.

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